

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Data Management Plan

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
<p>1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</p>	<p>Existing data will be used as references for comparison purpose only (example: S-K NEXAFS data of LiS batteries).</p> <p>This project re-used the following publicly available datasets:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experimental determination of differential scattering coefficients for nickel by means of linearly polarized x-ray radiation dataset <p>This data was collected to derive differential scattering coefficients for nickel.</p> 2. Hybrid Metrology for Nanostructured Optical Metasurfaces dataset <p>NEXAFS spectra were used to assess the crystallinity of TiO₂ nano-structures.</p> 3. Reference-free X-ray fluorescence analysis using well-known polychromatic synchrotron radiation dataset <p>This data was collected to investigate the feasibility of quantification using polychromatic sources</p> 4. Experimental determination of the sulfur K-shell fundamental parameters employing the holistic approach <p>Sulfur K-shell fundamental parameters will be used for sulfur quantification in operando studies of LiS batteries.</p> 5. Operando Measurement of Transition Metal Deposition in a NMC Li-Ion Battery Using Laboratory Confocal Micro-X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy <p>Laboratory data will be used as a baseline for follow up activities at synchrotron radiation facilities</p> 6. Operando X-ray Raman Ni 2p spectra of Li_{Nix}M_{ny}Co_{1-x-y}O₂ lithium-ion battery electrodes 7. Liquid Phase Infiltration of Block Copolymers <p>Literature data were used to carry out an in-depth review on the liquid phase infiltration process of block copolymers for the creation of plasmonic nanostructures.</p>

	<p>Data will be reused in follow-up activities. The next X-ray Raman beamtime is scheduled for February to May 2026.</p>
<p>2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?</p>	<p>Predominantly ASCII and HDF formats are provided by measurement instrumentation. Special data formats are used by measuring instrument's hardware/software/firmware. These formats are predominantly binary. Transfer into open access formats and adding of metadata is possible.</p> <p>The respective metadata will be generated in the following formats:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. graphics: jpeg, tiff, pdf, png, ptx, odg 2. tables: xlsx, odsu, opj 3. text: docx, pdf, txt
<p>3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p>Generation of scientific based upon measurement results within the work packages 1 to 4 for dissemination purposes in conferences, in reports, in standards and in open-access publications</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experimental determination of differential scattering coefficients for nickel by means of linearly polarized x-ray radiation dataset <p>The objective of this data is to provide a quantitative description of a sample of interest, for instance, to supplement an X-ray fluorescence analysis.</p> 2. Hybrid Metrology for Nanostructured Optical Metasurfaces dataset <p>The data was collected to obtain a traceable quantification of the physical and chemical quantities (i.e. refractive index, geometry, stoichiometry) of the nano-structures used for the realization of the SERS active windows</p> 3. Reference-free X-ray fluorescence analysis using well-known polychromatic synchrotron radiation dataset <p>The data was collected with the intention of advancing the determination of the elemental composition of a given bulk sample using polychromatic sources, i.e. a laboratory setup.</p> 4. Experimental determination of the sulfur K-shell fundamental parameters employing the holistic approach <p>Better knowledge on sulfur K-shell fundamental parameters will allow for sulfur quantification in operando studies of LiS batteries with lower uncertainties.</p> 5. Operando Measurement of Transition Metal Deposition in a NMC Li-Ion Battery Using Laboratory Confocal Micro-X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy <p>The provision of data enables manufacturers of laboratory equipment to better assess areas of application.</p> 6. Operando X-ray Raman Ni 2p spectra of $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$ lithium-ion battery electrodes <p>The provision of the data set will improve the assessment of the</p>

	<p>feasibility of the modern X-ray Raman method.</p> <p>7. Liquid Phase Infiltration of Block Copolymers</p> <p>The provision of the data set will help other groups investigating novel nanomaterials that have possible use as batterie operando cell components.</p>
<p>4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?</p>	<p>The expected data volume is unknown. Given that the majority of data sets are two-dimensional, it can be expected that the volume will be in the lower Gigabyte range.</p>
<p>5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?</p>	<p>Existing published open-access data and scientific literature. Partner's pre-existing measurement data in formats described under no. 2</p> <p>Predominantly ASCII and HDF formats are provided by measurement instrumentation. Special data formats are used by measuring instrument's hardware/software/firmware. These formats are predominantly binary. Transfer into open access formats and adding of metadata is possible</p> <p>The project has reused two datasets from external sources.</p> <p>The first is the x-ray mass absorption coefficient of low Z elements, which is a database from CXRO (https://cxro.lbl.gov/).</p> <p>The second is the x-ray mass absorption coefficient of transition metals, which is a database from xraylib (https://github.com/tschoonj/xraylib).</p> <p>The optical constants used for the ellipsometry modelling were extracted by J.A. Woollam software database (https://www.jawoollam.com/resources/reference-books).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experimental determination of differential scattering coefficients for nickel by means of linearly polarized x-ray radiation dataset <p>The objective of this data is to provide a quantitative description of a sample of interest, for instance, to supplement an X-ray fluorescence analysis.</p> 2. Hybrid Metrology for Nanostructured Optical Metasurfaces dataset <p>The data was collected to obtain a traceable quantification of the physical and chemical quantities (i.e. refractive index, geometry, stoichiometry) of the nano-structures used for the realization of the SERS active windows</p> 3. Reference-free X-ray fluorescence analysis using well-known polychromatic synchrotron radiation dataset <p>The data was collected with the intention of advancing the determination of the elemental composition of a given bulk sample using polychromatic sources, i.e. a laboratory setup.</p> 4. Experimental determination of the sulfur K-shell fundamental

	<p>parameters employing the holistic approach</p> <p>Better knowledge on sulfur K-shell fundamental parameters will allow for sulfur quantification in operando studies of LiS batteries with lower uncertainties.</p> <p>5. Operando Measurement of Transition Metal Deposition in a NMC Li-Ion Battery Using Laboratory Confocal Micro-X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy</p> <p>The provision of data enables manufacturers of laboratory equipment to better assess areas of application.</p> <p>6. Operando X-ray Raman Ni 2p spectra of Li_{Nix}MnyCo_{1-x-y}O₂ lithium-ion battery electrodes</p> <p>The provision of the data set will improve the assessment of the feasibility of the modern X-ray Raman method.</p> <p>7. Liquid Phase Infiltration of Block Copolymers</p> <p>The provision of the data set will help other groups investigating novel nanomaterials that have possible use as batterie operando cell components</p>
<p>6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	<p>The data will be useful for industrial stakeholders, R&D, science and standardization sectors.</p>

1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
<p>7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p>	<p>The project's open access peer-reviewed publications will each have a DOI. Internal data sets in the project will be assigned by other persistent and unique identifiers that allow for a DOI or equivalent assignment when they are stored in a repository.</p>
<p>8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</p>	<p>Data generated in the project and published in open access are discoverable by means of appropriate metadata (reflecting the key measurands and related operational parameters, see also point 9) according to the FAIR principles. Parts of the data produced will at time of generation not fulfil all FAIR requirements but can be upgraded to these by means of reprocessing (This refers to sort of intermediate data originating from alignment or test measurement).</p>
<p>9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</p>	<p>Yes, all project's datasets will be findable by their name, creation date and data type. Keywords will be added to the data set name. Metadata will be included into instrument/software-generated raw data files (e.g. measurement data files) were this option exists. Search keywords will be provided for use with datasets uploaded to repositories (Zenodo). General keywords may include: operando metrology, energy storage, etc. but also more specific keywords may be included, depending on the dataset type (e.g. x-ray fluorescence,</p>

	surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy, nanostructured materials, etc.)
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Metadata for use with datasets uploaded to a Zenodo repository will be harvested. Zenodo adheres to FAIR principles, guaranteeing that metadata is indexed and licensed under CC0 (Public Domain), except for email addresses. All metadata is exported through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and is available for harvesting.

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	All data for open access scientific publications will be made openly available in repository zenodo unless restrictions apply such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of third-party data without permission to publish them - Disclosure of the identity of a manufacturer without consent. - Data that compromises the protection of a partner(s) intellectual property. - Any data violating GDPR in agreement with section “D3 Ethics
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	The Zenodo repository has been successfully used in two former EMPIR projects of the same coordinator.
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Clear version identifiers will be used for man-made documents such as reports, protocols using numbering and other identifiers. Only one (the latest) version of a dataset will be uploaded to repositories (Zenodo) that can be expected to receive a unique identifier.
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	All open-access relevant data will be made openly available e.g. as a Zenodo repository to be confirmed by the project partners. In addition, project-internal non-open-access repositories (project file servers hosted by partners, share-point hosted by project coordinator organisation) will be used.
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research	No embargos are expected. In case that an embargo is to be applied the coordinator will try to limit this to 9 months in agreement with the respective partners.

Questions	Answers
data should be made available as soon as possible.	
16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?	The data will be accessible through the interface of the chosen open access Zenodo repository.
17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	Not applicable.
18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	The corresponding Zenodo protocols apply here. Open access repositories (such as Zenodo) have well described conditions.
19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	A data access committee is not necessary because the selection of data to be openly accessible will be made on a case-by-case basis by the partner(s). All partners have been informed and are aware of ethical aspects and data security such as for the protection of IP for any project outputs. It may be necessary to withhold all or some of the data generated. This will be decided by the relevant partner(s) associated with the respective dataset.
Metadata:	
20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	In zenodo, metadata will be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0 and is to contain information to enable the user to access the data. All metadata are exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested
21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?	The data will remain available and findable for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository, which is expected to be a minimum of 20 years. If data are withdrawn from Zenodo, the DOI and the URL of the original object are retained. In case of closure of the Zenodo repository, best efforts will be made by Zenodo to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.
22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	Interoperability can be assured if an external user 1) has the respective (e.g. hardware related) software available, 2) may use appropriate freeware or 3) after conversion of datasets into an open access format (e.g. ascii, csv, hdf...). The decision on one of the alternatives will be made on a case-by-case basis.

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you	Vocabularies will follow relevant conventions as laid down e.g. in applicable international fundamental or application standards, the SI system or other specifications such as vocabularies used in most prominent journals. In cases where a clear convention does not exist a thorough description of the data will ensure that data are interoperable. Vocabularies will follow relevant conventions as laid down e.g. in

follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?	applicable international fundamental or application standards, the SI system or other specifications such as vocabularies used in most prominent journals. In cases where a clear convention does not exist a thorough description of the data will ensure that data are interoperable.
24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow their re-use, refinement or extension?	For all datasets: the data, metadata and documentation are compliant to disciplinary standards; open file formats, controlled vocabularies and standard metadata scheme will be adopted for easy interoperability and re-use. The compatibility of chosen vocabularies with existing ontologies will be guaranteed through appropriate mappings
25 Will your data include qualified references ¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, e.g. atomic fundamental parameters. The project's datasets that will be deposited in the chosen repository (e.g. Zenodo) will include qualified references to other datasets from the same project

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?	Corresponding readme files on the methodology employed (e.g. XRD, XRS, Raman spectroscopy), definitions of measurands and operational parameters, and SI units applied are to be generated.
27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	Research data made public through publications, oral communications and posters. They will be made available as soon as reasonably possible and according to the project's work plan and be related to standard re-use licences in line with the grant agreement. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I. Murataj et al. "<i>Liquid Phase Infiltration of Block Copolymers</i>", Polymer 2022, 14 (20), 4317 - 10.3390/polym14204317, (INRiM), CC BY 4.0 DEED 2. I. Murataj et al. "<i>Hybrid Metrology for Nanostructured Optical Metasurfaces</i>", ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces 2023, 15, 50, 57992–58002 (INRiM, PTB), CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 DEED 3. A. Wählisch et al. "<i>Experimental determination of differential scattering coefficients for nickel by means of linearly polarized x-ray radiation</i>", Metrologia, 2023, 60 035001 (PTB), CC BY 3.0 DEED 4. A. Wählisch et al. "<i>Reference-free X-ray fluorescence analysis using well-known polychromatic synchrotron radiation</i>", J. Anal. At. Spectrom., 2023, 38, 1865-1873 (PTB), CC BY 4.0 DEED 5. I. Murataj et al. "<i>Artificial fingerprints engraved through block-copolymers as nanoscale physical unclonable functions for</i>

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/13-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Questions	Answers
	<p><i>authentication and identification</i>", Nat. Communications,15, 10576, 2024 – (INRiM), CC BY 4.0 DEED</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. P. Honicke, "Experimental determination of the sulfur K-shell fundamental parameters employing the holistic approach", New J. Phys. 26 103011 2024, CC BY 4.0 DEED 7. A. Rajh et al. "Sulfur Speciation in Li-S Batteries Determined by Operando Laboratory X-ray Emission Spectroscopy", ACS Appl. Energy Mater. 7(23),11135-11143, 2024 (JSI), CC BY 4.0 DEED 8. E. Cara et al. "Molecular surface coverage standards by reference-free GIXRF supporting SERS and SEIRA substrate benchmarking", DOI: 10.1515/nanoph-2024-02222024, (INRiM, PTB, CMI), CC BY 4.0 DEED 9. A. Zoccante et al. "The thermodynamics of self-assembled monolayer formation: a computational and experimental study of thiols on a flat gold surface", Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 26, 18799-18807, 2024 – (INRiM, PTB, CMI), CC BY 4.0 DEED 10. G. Greco et al. "The Behavior of the Intercalant AlCl4 Anion during the Formation of Graphite Intercalation Compound: An X-ray Absorption Fine Structure Study", DOI: 10.1002/pssa.202300776, 2024 (URoma1, PTB), CC BY 4.0 DEED 11. M. Argostini et al. "Coupling of S@aerogel and Si/SiOx Nanospheres Electrodes with "Polysulfide" Salt-Free Electrolytes in a Fluorine-Free Lithium-Ion Batteries", Small Struct., 2500096, 2025 (UNIROMA1), CC BY 4.0 DEED 12. I. Mantouvalou et al. "Operando Measurement of Transition Metal Deposition in a NMC Li-Ion Battery Using Laboratory Confocal Micro-X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy", Small 2025, 2502460 (TUB, PTB, WWU), CC BY 4.0 DEED 13. A. Jonas et al. "Operando X-ray Raman Ni 2p spectra of LiNixMnyCo1-x-yO2 lithium-ion battery electrodes", DOI: 10.1557/s43580-025-01397-3 2025 (PTB, Empa, MEU), CC BY 4.0 DEED 14. B. Bouabadi et al. "Morphological Evolution of Sn-Metal-Based Anodes for Lithium-Ion Batteries Using Operando X-Ray Imaging", Advanced Science 12(10) 2025 (HZB), CC BY 4.0 DEED 15. K. Bzheumikhova et al. "Enhancing the efficiency of a wavelength-dispersive spectrometer based on a slitless design using a single-bounce monocrystalline" JINST 32(PT 1):171-179, 2025 (PTB), CC BY 4.0 DEED 16. A. Rulev et al. "Operando NRVS on LiFePO4 Battery with 57Fe Phonon DOS", Crystals 15, 841, 2025 (EMPA), CC BY 4.0 DEED
<p>28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</p>	<p>The data generated by this project will be usable for third parties such as end users of the industrial tools as well as for the R&D department of companies associated with the project as unfunded partner or collaborator. Any data published in open-access journals will be usable by third parties after the datasets have been deposited in Zenodo. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications will be made available for re-use on a case-by-case basis</p>
<p>29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</p>	<p>Yes, the data quality will be assured through internal quality assurance processes (such as SOPs, calibration, maintenance, data backup concepts) of the partner organisations. ISO 17025 compatible systems will be applied by the accredited partner organisations.</p>
<p>30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</p>	<p>For SI traceable data the quality assurance involves calibrated instrumental and well-known fundamental parameters or reference material parameters for physical or chemical traceability chains, respectively.</p>

Questions	Answers
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	SOPs to be generated shall implement other research outputs where adequate. This will involve instrumental or measurement concepts as well as experience from optimal modelling approaches.

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	Relevant workflows, protocols, measurement modelling and materials constituents will be documented either in SOPs or open-access publications of the project.
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	The management of other research outputs shall enter internal quality management procedures, preferably in line with ISO 17025 regulations, and SOP generations. As far as possible, the FAIR data approaches specified in questions 7-30 above will be applied to the management of this project's other research outputs.

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	The fulfilment of the FAIR principles will entail personal costs around 2000 €.
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	Associated costs for dataset preparation and data management during the project will be covered by the project itself (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).
36 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	All participating project partners will be responsible, with the coordinator taking special responsibilities for the overall management

37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?	The long-term preservation will bring no additional costs. The value of the data is mainly due to use in a publication / proof of good scientific practice will be ensured by depositing the data within repositories (Zenodo, PTB's open access repository); re-use in subsequent projects or by others; self-commitment.
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1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	In compliance with ISO 17025 data repositories and data backup options from partner organisations will be used. Migration of all project data to these facilities can be assured. Temporary data storage on other storage devices (such as computer hard discs, USB sticks) is permissible if in accordance with SOPs.
39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes, the data will be safely stored in the Zenodo open access repository. Zenodo and the underlying Invenio Framework for digital repositories were designed according to the Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS) reference model.

1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	No ethical issues will have an impact on data sharing or legal issues.
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	The project does not deal with personal data.

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	The data management will be compliant to the research data policy of the funder: Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf)

2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the	Or, list any exceptions to this
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e.g. 23FUN01, 23NRM01 short name

	box to confirm	
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	